

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF MULTIMEDIA, COMMUNICATION AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN ACADEMIC LYCEUMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14506234>

***Abstract.** The article reflects on the course of the digitalization process, which is relevant today on a global scale, as well as the meaning and role of digital transformation and multimedia communication, which is one of the important processes in digitalization.*

***Keywords:** digitalization, communication, multimedia, digital transformation.*

The purpose of the transition to digital education is to ensure that each student achieves the knowledge and skills required at each stage of the educational institution (defined in the curriculum) quickly and without difficulties. On the basis of such a model, the student will be able to use all forms of education.

Today, the relevance of educational transformation is due to changes aimed at overcoming the contradictions between the socio – economic development and the specific rapid characteristics of transformation processes, which are carried out uniformly in education.

The relevance of transforming education today is related to changes aimed at overcoming the contradictions between the specific rapid characteristics of social and economic development and transformation processes being implemented uniformly in education.

One day, whether we want it or not, a digital future will unfold, and communication and multimedia will occupy a central role in its prospects. We have observed and used various forms of communication throughout different periods. The different forms of communication have been relevant in their respective eras. Over time, new forms of communication have emerged. However, the old forms of communication have not lost their significance. For example, the emergence of writing and the printing press led to the creation of books, which remain relevant today. The evolution of multimedia, including electricity (telegraph, telephone, sound recording), mass media (cinema, television, radio), and digital technologies (computers, the Internet), is the result of the formation and development of mass media in each era, primarily the formation and growth of digital mass media.

The process of shaping the digital world incorporates several evolutions, with its initial stages being automation and digitization. We carry out the process of digitization through digital transformation. Digital transformation involves the application of innovative and digital technologies to commercial processes, improving efficiency, optimizing costs, increasing productivity, and ensuring the competitiveness of organizations. Similarly, digital transformation involves changing people's material worldviews, business models, and organizational processes, as they must adapt to the rapidly changing technological environment and meet the demands of modern customers worldwide.

In the context of digital transformation, various technologies can be applied. Some of these technologies include artificial intelligence, cloud technology, the Internet of Things (IoT),

blockchain technology, and others. The role of multimedia technologies is invaluable in the optimal use of a combination of these technologies. Now, we will examine some of the connections between multimedia communication and digital transformation.

In the development of modern education today, the digital transformation of education is considered an important resource that requires a fundamental change in students' thinking patterns. Such changes may include the following:

Updating the content of education;

Updating the organizational forms and methods of educational activities;

Continuously evaluating educational outcomes based on achievements and planned activities;

Ensuring the integration of new technologies in all important areas of human activity;

Implementing drastic changes in technology, culture, and interaction processes.

Thus, the stages of implementing digital transformation processes in education can be expressed as follows, based on their evolution (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Stages of Digital Transformation in the Education Process.

The dynamic growth of the technical and economic characteristics of high-tech innovative products helps significantly increase the computational power and intellectual potential of products, as well as rapidly change the outdated standards and technological platforms of information and communication systems and networks. At the same time, ultra-high-speed networks, mobile devices, and the operation of information systems are aimed at improving the quality of multimedia content and the quality of large-scale services provided to the population.

Digital transformation can be imagined as a new idea or technology promoted by some advanced companies in the world. The emergence of new technologies and products may create simple communication with consumers, but in order to establish sufficiently fast and high-quality

communication, the company or institution must be fully equipped. Digital transformation requires a good and financially stable consumer. This phrase can be interpreted as follows:

First, the educational institution where digital transformation must be implemented should be financially stable, have a high scientific potential, and ensure foreign cooperation.

Second, the educational institution (consumer) accepting this transformation process must understand who or what is involved, what environment it is operating in, and what development strategy it is choosing.

Third, the level of employment, which is one of the global issues in the world, including in our Republic, will have a positive or negative impact on the working potential of the institution.

The multimedia competence of teachers, that is, their literacy, and multimedia communications provide technical and software compatibility in the digitization of any information society. Multimedia communications involve the process of encoding, receiving, and transmitting information through local communication networks, optimally using external devices and channels, and visualizing them on various display devices.

In conclusion, we can emphasize that multimedia communication ensures the participation of students and teachers in various projects as a team, working in a team, making quick decisions, distributing responsibilities among team members, saving time, developing a culture of professional interaction, and establishing a culture of communication with multimedia tools and project participants.

Thus, in our final conclusion, we can highlight that these activities are applied in class and extracurricular processes, in additional education, in educational courses and centers, as well as in various forums, competitions, and entertainment events.

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